

《万有引力原理、量子引力方程、反重力模型、反引力的几个思想试验》

节选说明：

此前我发的文章《光速不变原理中的关键性错误-在测量光速时忽略了光子波函数坍缩和重新生成的过程》中，这个成果是所有理论中最最简单的，但却是整个理论体系中最后才悟到的。

为了让大家能更好的理解我的理论体系，现将我的书籍节选一部分奉献给大家。之所以不能将整篇书籍放在网上，是因为书中大部分内容并不是人们常见的论文的方式。

后面文章均节选自：

Overview of the New Concept Physics: 新概念物理学概述，ISBN: 9798884820197。

该书在 amazon 个人发表。

The Principle of Gravity, the Quantum Gravity Equation, the Anti-Gravity Model, and a Few Thought Experiments in Anti-Gravity

Excerpt Description:

In my previous posting, “Critical Error in the Principle of the Invariance of the Speed of Light - Neglecting the Process of Photon Wave Function Collapse and Regeneration in Measuring the Speed of Light” , this result is the simplest and most simple of all the theories, but it is the last to be enlightened in the whole system of theories.

In order for you to better understand my theoretical system, an excerpt of my book is now dedicated to you. The reason why I can't put the whole book online is because most of the content in the book is not in the way that people commonly see in papers.

All the articles that follow are excerpted from:

Translated with DeepL.com (free version)

Overview of the New Concept Physics: 新概念物理学概述, ISBN: 9798884820197。

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第三章 万有引力的原理及量子引力方程

人们知道,爱因斯坦先生在广义相对论中用引力场方程描述了处于时空中的物质通过质量影响、弯曲周围的时空几何空间,被弯曲的时空影响物质运动。即时空告诉物体如何运动,物体告诉时空如何弯曲。广义相对论解释了很多牛顿引力理论无法解释的现象。但是,根据我发现的人们在光速测量中存在的重要疏忽(在本文第一章已经描述),该疏忽的发现已经足够动摇相对论的理论基础。

在量子力学中,人们提出了引力子的假说,可惜直到现在也没有找到引力子的存在证据。

除以上两个最有代表性的理论外,人们对万有引力的形成原理众说纷纭,但没有一个能够接近事实真相。

我在思考万有引力的原理时,没有参考任何人的著作。直觉告诉我所有的物理定律一定有一个底层的逻辑,而且一定是互相兼容的。所以我从运动、相对空间着手,慢慢的抽丝剥茧,终于发现了万有引力的原理。该原理简单明了,最终还能够进行扩展,在扩展的过程中也不会出现任何问题。

1. 万有引力原理

A、B 为两个相对静止的粒子。在 A、B 中,其内部的电磁波在自己的空间体系里以光速传播,在空间中仅存

在 A, 或仅存在 B 时, 两个粒子没有任何的相互作用(图 3.1)。

图3.1: 独立观察相对空间时

当在空间中同时观察 A、B 两个粒子时, 两个粒子在相互的视角中出现了视角角度的变化。如图 3.2, A、B 相距为 R , 在 A 的视角观察 B 时, B 处于以 A 为顶点的圆锥中。B 的距离越大视角圆锥角度越小, 距离越小视角圆锥角度越大。在以 A 为球心以 R 为半径的球面上存在无数个点, 与 B 点等效。A 与 B 存在着不同的相对空间。在视角圆锥的基础上, 结合相对空间即可找到万有引力最终的基本原理。

图3.2: 相对空间之间的视角圆锥

取 B 在球面上的任意位置, 与 A 共同观察, 如图 3.3:

图3.3: 相对空间之间的视角圆锥

在 A、B 两个粒子的内部，其电磁波在各自的空间体系中以光速传播。当单独观察其中一个粒子时，其电磁波对其他的空间体系没有作用。

当同时观察两个粒子时：B 的电磁波在 B 的相对空间传播的同时，也是在 A 的视角圆锥中传播；A 的电磁波在 A 的相对空间传播的同时，也是在 B 的视角圆锥中传播。

根据图 3.3 可以推导出以下两种作用：

一、A 的相对空间与其包含的所有电磁波，对 A 以外的相对空间形成了视角，A 的电磁波总量作用于视角，形成了视角的密度和结构。

当 A 的电磁波总量的增减，会造成外部视角密度的增减。

二、B 内部的电磁波在传播的过程中，相对于 A 的相对空间出现了相对空间密度的变化：

在趋向 A 的方向上，B 的电磁波相对于 A 的相对空

间的密度随时间增加；

在远离 A 的方向上，B 的电磁波相对于 A 的相对空间的密度随时间减小。

B 的电磁波相对于 A 的相对空间，产生了趋向 A 的整体差别——B 的电磁波穿过的属于 A 的相对空间，远离 A 的稀疏、靠近 A 的密集，在 A 的相对空间，B 的电磁波出现了整体的趋向 A 的趋势。

综合一、二可知，在 A 的视角密度和结构的作用下，B 的电磁波出现的整体的趋向 A 的能量趋势，这种趋势形成了趋向 A 的能量差值，正是这导致了万有引力。

当 A 和 B 的视角对换结果不变。

视角可以叠加，A 与 B 都可以是一个物体的全部原子，也可以是一片海洋，也可以是一个星球，也可以是一个星系。

——这就是在新思路下得到的“万有引力原理”。

2. 量子引力方程

根据“万有引力原理”可以推导出量子引力方程，并进一步证明该原理的正确性。

在此次推导过程中，均采用能量来解释相关的公式。

如图 3.4：粒子 A 的“相对空间”及“相对空间包含的能量”对粒子 B 形成的视角作用，在粒子 B 处形成了以 R 为半径的球面。

图3.4: 相对空间作用的密度

将图 3.4 局部放大, 得到图 3.5。在图中, 粒子 A 与粒子 B 的距离为 R , 粒子 A 的质量为 M 、能量为 E , 粒子 B 的质量为 m , 能量为 e , 圆周率为 π ,

图3.5: 相对空间作用的密度

A 的所有能量相对于 B, 作用到以 A 为球心, 以 R 为半径的球面上, 那么粒子 A 相对于粒子 B 处的相对空间作用密度(能量密度)为 $\frac{E}{4\pi R^2}$ 。

根据“万有引力原理”, 粒子 B 相对于 A 的作用空间出现了能量差。粒子 B 中向各个方向传播的能量可以简化(如图 3.6), 其中仅计取朝向 A 的能产生万有引力的部分能量 ab^+ , 其数量为 $(1/2)^3$ 。

如图 3.6 所示，在 ab^+ 能量 $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3$ 中， θ 角以外的部分能量需抵消在 ab^+ 方向上远离 A 的能量，不计入公式中； θ 角以内的能量，其数量为 $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta$ ，产生了朝向 A 的能量趋势。

图3.6: 在相对空间作用下的能量差

产生的能量趋势是指 $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta$ 这部分能量，在向 A 的方向传播的过程中，在 A 的视角圆锥中被压缩而出现的能量密度提高的现象，“能量密度提高的数量”就形成了能量差 Δe 。在计算 Δe 时，根据不确定性原理，不能按粒子 B 的几何空间计算相对于 A 的视角圆锥的体积变化，需要把在 B 中传播的所有能量视为在 A 的相对空间传播。那么，相对于粒子 A 的空间，粒子 B 中的电磁波向各个方向传播，形成了以粒子 B 质心为球心的电磁波球体。与粒子 A 相对于粒子 B 处的相对空间作用的面积 $\frac{1}{4\pi R^2}$ 相对应，粒子 B 相对于 A 的视角圆锥的体积变化为 $\frac{1}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$ 。那

么，粒子 B 相对于 A 的作用空间出现的能量差 $\Delta e =$

$$\frac{e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}。$$

A 的相对空间作用密度(能量密度)与 B 的能量变化相乘就是“导致 B 被 A 吸引的能量”。

合并后形成下列公式：

$$\frac{F}{g} c^2 = \frac{E}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 e \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$$

整理可得量子引力方程：

$$F = \frac{M c^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 m c^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$$

简化后公式：

$$F = \frac{M m}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin \theta}{128\pi^2 c}$$

其中 c 为光速， g 为地面的重力加速度。其中 $\frac{3g \sin \theta}{128\pi^2 c}$ 为“万有引力常数”的数学表达式，如果将粒子 A 视为地球，则其物理意义为：地球相对于地面物体的单位空间能量密度与地面物体单位能量之间的引力系数。

在方程 $F = \frac{M c^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 m c^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$ 中，粒子 A 相对于粒

子 B 处的相对空间作用 $\frac{1}{4\pi R^2}$ ，粒子 B 相对于 A 的视角圆

锥的体积变化 $\frac{1}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$ ，这两个内容为本文所述引力原理的核心。

在公式中，粒子的能量用爱因斯坦质能方程 $E = mc^2$ 计算，圆周率 π 按3.141592654计算，光速 c 为299,792,458米/秒，重力加速度 g 视为常数，按9.807。 θ 角的取值如图3.6所示，当 θ 角取值在 60° 以内时，这部分能量形成了引力。

将数据代入公式得 $\frac{3g \sin 60}{128\pi^2 c}$ ，所得“万有引力常数”值为 $6.72736 \cdot 10^{-11}$ ，与原数值 $6.67387 \cdot 10^{-11}$ 差别小于0.795%。其原因：公式 $F = \frac{Mm}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin 60}{128\pi^2 c}$ 为量子引力，比地面实测物体的万有引力稍大。

第一个原因，在方程中， $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin 60$ 为能量 $ab^{\sim}$ 的近似值，未来可以采取更精确的方式来计算；

第二个原因，在地面的实际测量中，地球自转、地球半径与地球结构各层的密度变化不可忽略，导致实测值较量子引力值稍小， θ 角的取值也应当略小于 60° 。也可以理解为在地面测量的是粒子相对于“地球的粒子集合”的引力，由于地球密度不均匀，越近地心密度越大，那么 θ 角的取值也应当略小于 60° 。

根据推算，当 θ 角取值约为 59.22° 时，形成万有引力方程 $F = \frac{Mm}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin 59.22}{128\pi^2 c}$ ，计算结果完全符合人们在地面上测得的结果。

3. 量子引力方程的普适性

量子引力方程具有最大程度的普适性,可以适用于各种参考系。在量子引力方程中:

$$F = \frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 mc^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$$

$\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3$ 的物理意义为以粒子 B 质心为球心的电磁波球体,相对于任何一个方向均是光速,产生的万有引力与粒子 B 的运动状态无关,无论粒子 B 以何种方式运动,也不论粒子 B 的运动速度多高,只要粒子 A 的“相对空间作用”已经在 B 的相对空间处存在,就不会改变量子引力方程的客观基础。在引力的形成过程中,所有的能量不需要在相对空间之间进行转换,遵循光速不变原理,粒子因相对运动而导致的“质能增量”与引力的形成无关。

另外,在文中 g 被视为常数的原因是人们在物理学的发展过程中,在地面对质量、能量、力、长度、速度、加速度等进行了一系列的规定,而 g 是在这些物理度量之间已经形成的固有的常数。在公式中,不能因参考系的变化而采取不同的 g 值。

4. 大质量星体的引力方程

上述量子引力方程在应用于大质量星体时,需要考虑大质量星体的引力造成的电磁波蓝移和红移的比值。在图 3.5 中,如果 a 为质量较大的星体, a 的引力将造成 b 的能量出现引力蓝移和引力红移,相同的电磁波在蓝移方向的能量比红移方向更大,所以大质量星体对物体的相对空间作用更大,那么,星体 a 的相对空间在 b 点的作用密度为 $\frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{f_b}{f_r}$, 其中 f_b 为电磁波蓝移频率, f_r 为红移频率。得到大质量星体的引力方程:

$$F = \frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{f_b}{f_r} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 mc^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}。$$

这种情况与广义相对论类似,但根本原理完全不同。广义相对论是建立在光速不变、仅考虑坐标系变换、不考虑相对空间转换的基础上的,是唯象理论。

第四章 克服万有引力的方法、万有斥力、反重力模型

在万有引力原理的指导下，以相对空间、相对空间作用、相对空间转换，能量差与能量趋势等概念为基础，继续引申思考，即可推导出克服万有引力的方法。

1. 人造地球卫星围绕地球旋转克服引力的原理解析

在所有克服万有引力的方法中，人造地球卫星围绕地球旋转是人类最早发现的方法，也是众所周知的方法之一。

我们一般通过圆周或椭圆运动来克服万有引力，我们说圆周或椭圆运动产生了离心力，人们将离心力定义为惯性作用力。在深入思考万有引力和反引力时可以发现，人们的定义并没有深入理解到物质的更深层次原理，将离心力定义为惯性作用力仍然是唯象理论。

如图 4.1, 图4.1: 人造卫星的离心力原理

假设 A 为地球，B 为人造卫星。如果 B 与 A 相对静止，B 将在 A 的视角圆锥的作用下被 A、B 两者间

的万有引力吸引，最终 B 将坠落在地球 A 上。

现在我们在地球 A 的切线方向上将 B 加速到第一宇宙速度，这时我们说 B 相对于 A 产生了离心力，即惯性作用力。在该力的作用下 B 将围绕地球 A 作圆周运动。

那么离心力的原理是怎样的呢？——该原理可以用相对空间转换来解析。

在阐述离心力原理前，首先需要明白离心力与万有引力存在一个关键的不同点：

万有引力：两个空间体系间的视角造成，两者的相对空间作用与两个空间体系的运动状态无关，所以无论 A、B 以何种方式运动，也不论相对运动速度的高低，只要 A 或 B 的相对空间作用已经在对方所在相对空间存在，万有引力总是存在的。

离心力：属于运动过程中产生的力的作用，该作用遵循运动的特性，在不考虑相对空间转换时，A、B 两者不存在差别。在考虑相对空间转换时，B 相对于 A 出现了运动方向上的能量差。

如图 4.2.1，我们将 B 内部的电磁波简化，只保留在运动方向和运动反方向传播的电磁波。根据引力原理和运动原理的描述，要审视 B 相对于 A 运动时产生的力，需要找到 B 相对于 A 的能量差（能量趋势）。

图4.2: 人造卫星的离心力原理

如图 4.2.2, 在完成相对空间转换后:

电磁波 W_1 转换为 W_1' , 波长变小、频率变大, 能量变大;

电磁波 W_2 转换为 W_2' , 波长变长、频率变小, 能量变小。

于是, B 在运动方向上出现了整体的能量差, 这个能量差形成了离心力。

以上就是离心力的根本原理。

在圆周运动中, B 运动形成的能量差随时远离 A, 其效果与万有引力造成的能量差(能量趋势)大小相等、方向相反。

2. 平面形粒子的第二种特殊情况

粒子 A 为普通粒子, 粒子 B 为一个平面形粒子, 粒

子 B 的平面垂直于 AB 连线，如图 4.3。

图4.3: 平面粒子的第二种特殊情况

在粒子 B 中，粒子 B 包含的所有电磁波均在 B 的圆形边缘旋转传播，电磁波的传播方向遵循波形震荡，某时刻呈现顺时针方向传播（如图 4.3.1），下一时刻呈现逆时针方向传播（如图 4.3.2）。这时我们通过相对空间转换分析粒子 B 相对于粒子 A 的能量差（能量趋势）。

如图 4.3.3，在完成相对空间转换后，所有的电磁波的传播方向均垂直于 B 的切线，且与“B 的切点与 A 的连接线”相互垂直。此时，粒子 B 的全部能量均呈现远离 A 的能量趋势，粒子 B 相对于粒子 A 呈现完全的斥力作用。

再审视图 4.3.1 和图 4.3.2，当粒子 B 的电磁波不进行相对空间转换时，所有的电磁波同样垂直于“B 的切点与 A 的连接线”，粒子 B 与粒子 A 同样呈现斥力作用。这种情形，其原理与“两个普通粒子间的万有引力”完全相同，我将其命名为万有斥力。万有斥力与万有引力性质相同，方向相反，属于长程力。

粒子 B 是中微子的粒子模型。

在此基础上，可以划分出新的基本作用力。

万有斥力可以在第四种基本作用力的基础上，被列为第五种基本作用力。另外，核外电子和物质分子中，两个或多个电子形成的化学键力（在后文描述），可以被列为第六种基本作用力。

如粒子 B 一样的粒子在其平面的垂线上运动时，不受惯性影响的同时，由于与星体之间的斥力作用，可以超越光速，其条件是该星体的空间作用已经在该粒子所经过的空间存在。另一方面，由于这种粒子与其他粒子之间存在斥力作用，且粒子距离越近斥力越大，使它即使以极高的速度运动，也难以与其他粒子相撞，甚至可以轻松的穿越致密的固体。这是超光速中微子现象的完美解释，即解释了中微子的作用原理，也解释了超光速现象。

在 2011 年时，我曾经密切关注欧洲核子研究中心 (CERN) 对超光速中微子的发现，遗憾的是公开的资料显示试验是失败的。但是我的理论支持他们。

人们可以模仿这种粒子模型来克服万有引力。

3. 几种反重力装置

第一种：

如图 4.4，在水平的可以绕垂直的轴旋转的圆形平面上缠绕超导线圈并固定。导入一定量的电能，就会产生与重力方向相反的升力。或者在固定为圆环形的光纤线圈中

输入激光亦可。

图4.4: 在平面上缠绕超导线圈

升力的大小与输入的能量成正比、与距离星体质心间的距离的平方成反比。

我们要克服万有引力的所有办法的关键在于,能够沿星体作用空间的球面切线产生整体能量差,形成远离的趋势。

可以预见,当输入的能量足够大,就能产生比万有引力更大的力,使该装置加速远离地球,使大距离的空间旅行成为简单的事情。传说中的飞碟,必定是以这种方式获得克服万有引力的作用力的。

第二种:

一个直径较大的圆盘呈水平面放置,圆盘的边缘质量较大,中心质量较小,当整个圆盘以超高速自旋,圆盘边缘的线速度超过第一宇宙速度后,圆盘将随着转速的提高获得反重力。

第三种

制作质量较轻、能量较大的圆环形高能粒子加速器，在加速器中通过磁场把许多高能粒子控制在环形轨道中运行，当全部高能粒子的动能总量满足反重力的要求，同样可以获得反重力。

第四种

在环形或球形容容器内模仿“平面形粒子的第二种特殊情况”。需要在如图 4.4 所示的垂直于引力重心连线的平面上，通过控制电磁波的传播路径，在平面或容器中让所有的电磁波或光子呈现循环振荡。当人类科技发展到较高水平，通过第四种方式直接模仿“平面形粒子的第二种特殊情况”，满足第五种基本作用力的形成条件后，将会成为克服万有引力的最佳方法。

所有反重力装置的共同点：围绕垂直于重力线的环形装置中形成旋转的能量差。

在未来，人类可以采取多种方式克服重力影响，在造物主的引导下成为星际文明。

第五章 万有引力和反引力的几个思想试验及思考

在前面两章中，我们知道了万有引力和反引力的原理，如果我们以上帝视角观察，可以得到万有引力和反引力的几种特殊形式，也可得到粒子的相对空间与宇宙空间相连的特殊形式。正是这些特殊形式才使我们的宇宙具有至高无上的无私大德，拥有无限未来和无限可能，宇宙不会成为“坍缩-爆炸”的循环体或超级黑洞、也没有热寂或死亡的终点。

下面简要叙述这几种特殊形式：

1. 万有引力并不总是相互的

为了解释这个远远超越常识的知识，让我们来一次超级思想试验吧。当然，下面的思想试验是人们不敢想的，更不可能写在任何的论文中。但是为了解释万有引力并不总是相互的作用力，这个试验是必须要阐述的。

让我们来设计这样一个试验：上帝至善万能，有一天他想欣赏一下地球的美景，于是打了一个响指，让整个太阳系刹那暂停，暂时取消了星球间所有的互相作用力，取消了已经发出的所有的光。所有星球都看不到其他星球，所有人也看不到其他人。

……他把地球暂时拿走了——要在天堂里展示一下地球的美景。

然后，上帝让响指的影响消失。太阳重新发出光，而且光开始传播。时间过去了一会儿，太阳光到达了地球原来所在位置，太阳一愣，地球去哪了？因为没有发现地球，太阳也就感觉不到地球的万有引力。

当然，太阳需要忙的事情很多，来不及思考地球的去向，光继续传播。

过了几秒钟，上帝把地球放回了原位。

放回原位之后……响指！第二次的响指仅是暂停，不取消所有的一切。

这时，当然可以想象一下这个时刻的引力是什么样。

在这个时刻：太阳光已经照耀在地球所在位置，太阳的相对空间的对外作用已经在地球这个位置存在。

地球立刻受到太阳的万有引力影响。

可是，地球被放回原位这件事，太阳还没看到，也不知道，因为地球的相对空间作用还没有传递到太阳那边，太阳也没有受到地球的万有引力的影响！

这时，我们发现了一个常规物理学中不可能发生的事情：万有引力并不总是相互的。

然后，第二次响指的影响消失，所有的一切继续。

8分钟后，太阳看到了地球反射的光，地球的相对空间作用也传播到了太阳的位置。

太阳重新感受到了地球的万有引力。然后太阳系的一切恢复正常。

这个思想试验说明了一件事：**万有引力并不总是相互的，彻底突破了“力的相对性”**。这是力学存在的问题，

人们总是设想力是由物质或粒子传递——事实并非如此，我们都在虚妄中迷茫，没有看清真相。如果再深入追加一个问题，就是**所有的力学都需要考虑光速**，需要考虑上帝视角。

引力不会超距实时传递，在大尺度下的引力并不总是相互的，这个特点保持了宇宙的稳定。

粒子中的电磁波及粒子的相对空间作为一个整体，对外部空间存在“相对空间作用”。这种相对作用无法超越光速。一个粒子产生，对空间的作用以光速传播，该作用传播到其他粒子时，其他粒子开始受到该粒子的引力。在这个粒子产生之前，如果其他粒子的“相对空间作用”在该粒子产生的位置已经存在影响，该粒子从产生起，立刻受到其他粒子的引力。而该粒子的空间作用传播到其他粒子的位置之前，其他粒子不会受到该粒子的引力。万有引力并不总是相互的，这取决于“相对空间作用”存在和传播的情况。“相对空间作用”传播的过程，其对外表现就是引力波，引力波只是一种表面现象，不能用引力波来定义或解释引力。

2. 反引力并不总是相互的

后面这个思想试验就更加简单，但道理将更加深邃：在某个时刻，一个反引力装置（以下简称为“飞碟”）在距离地球 300,000km 的高空突然运行了半秒，然后关机。

在飞碟“运行的半秒”时间段中，飞碟受到了地球的

反引力。

地球大约在飞碟关机半秒后开始受到飞碟的反引力作用力，且“持续了半秒”。在持续的“两个半秒”的时间段中，两者受到的作用力均是单向作用。

在飞碟关机后、地球还没有收到飞碟反引力的半秒中，两者之间没有反引力存在。

当然，人们可以用“时空”解释这一切，也能在可怜的“时空”理论里自洽。但是，将来人们利用量子纠缠全面实现信息的“实时”、“超距”传递的时候，利用飞碟实现超光速旅行的时候，也要坚守时空的谬论吗？所谓“时空”已经阻碍科学发展近百年，人类寿命即使以200年计，所处光球的半径也不过可怜的200光年。人们不想突破这个可怜的认知障碍吗？

当然，你如果坚持时空的观点，那么我再给你一个试验，看你如何用时空来解释这一切。

3. 在大尺度空间中力的作用并不总是相互的

假设有一个地球规模的巨型飞碟在距离地球1光年的地方超高速飞行。在此位置，太阳和地球的相对空间作用已经在飞碟的飞行路径上存在。在某时刻，该飞碟利用太阳和地球的相对空间作用产生的反引力以便降低飞行速度，该时间持续了大约十分钟，飞碟实现了其减速的目的，于是暂时关机并停止反作用力的作用。由于该飞碟是地球规模的巨型飞碟，其产生的反引力极大，如果地球在

一年后受到该力的作用，一定会有非常明显的感受。

过了半年，该飞碟在距离地球 1 亿公里处掠过并飞向远方。

又过了半年，飞碟发出的“能够产生反引力的相对空间作用”穿过了太阳和地球“两年前所处的位置”。此时，地球和太阳均没有受到飞碟一年前发出的持续了十分钟的反引力的作用。

推论：力的作用并不总是相互的。

4. 反引力对近距离物体的作用

由于引力与反引力一样，都呈现距离的平方反比关系。人类可以巧妙的设计飞碟，使得反引力在推动飞碟克服引力做超高加速度运动的同时，推动飞碟中的“生物和物体的每个粒子”以相同的加速度运动，以超高加速度实现超光速，实现真正自由的星际之旅。

当反引力足够强大，将对近距离的物体形成足够强的斥力，对任何靠近的物质将会急剧减速（对物体施加较大的反向加速度），如电影特效中幻想的那样，形成以飞碟为球心的“能量护盾”。在特定方向的反引力的作用下，能够把高速撞向飞碟的物体的速度减速到零，然后实现反弹。

同时，反引力装置周围的物质分子同样会受到斥力作用，使反引力装置隔离空气分子和水分子，在空气中超音速运动不会出现音爆，在海洋中运动时受到水的阻力影响

也会非常小。如果反引力装置产生的斥力足够强大，能够隔绝所有高速运动的粒子，能够进入地球内部岩浆，甚至进入恒星的内部。

5. 能量守恒定律的局限

飞碟的能量增加到一定程度，在任意的空间位置都将产生大于万有引力的斥力，此后飞碟将加速远离地球。可以预见的是，要克服万有引力，输入线圈的能量必须超过克服第一宇宙速度所拥有的动能。当飞碟离开地球的引力范围，同样可以用上述的办法来克服引力更加强大的星球、甚至星系的束缚，走向真正的星际自由之旅。只要飞碟的能量足够大，持续以高加速度来远离地球，到达目的地时持续以高加速度来减速，那么从地球到月球可以只用几分钟，到火星可以只用几个小时，甚至更少。

飞碟产生的反引力的原理，与人们之前所总结的物理学、力学完全不同。甚至违反了之前的物理学中两个最为重要的定律：

一是它不需要抛出物质来实现反作用力，如果不用我提供的这个理论来解释，会违反动量守恒定律；

二是随着克服万有引力的作用力的影响，远离的速度将随着时间的增加而增加，此时，速度的增加不需要消耗更多的能量。这种运动方式将从根本上冲击传统的动能、势能理论体系，与传统物理中最重要的定律——能量守恒定律产生不可调和的矛盾。

产生矛盾的原因，首先，这是因为没有在能量守恒定律中引入“相对空间作用”这一个概念。其次，继续深入探究能量守恒定律就会发现，并不是能量不守恒，而是能量守恒定律存在着一定的局限性——没有对动能和势能从更深层次的意义上进行定义和解释。而要解释动能和势能，就需要对电磁波及其相对空间进行深入的了解。

6. 重新定义势能

势能与动能的本质不同，要区分它们，需要更加深入探讨万有引力对空间体系的影响。

如图 5.1，假设 A 为地球，B 为一个粒子。当 B 离地面较高时，B 在 A 的视角圆锥中产生的能量差（能量趋势）较小；当 B 离地面较低时，B 在 A 的视角圆锥中产生的能量差（能量趋势）较大。B 在两个不同距离上的能量差（能量趋势）出现了差值，该差值就是势能的变化。

图5.1: 势能

图5.1.1 距离远时能量差较小

图5.1.2 距离近时能量差较大

粒子势能的变化是由于不同空间距离下，粒子中的电磁波相对于另一空间体系的不平衡的差别程度引起。相对于地球的作用空间，离地面越低，这种相对不平衡越大，势能越小；在较高的位置相对不平衡较小，势能越大。这是从本质上论述势能，这与人们对势能的定量描述无矛盾。

在一定的高度，这种相对空间的不平衡处于一定水平，如果改变高度，必然引起不平衡程度的改变。由于粒子的相对空间及其电磁波组成的空间体系对空间属性的保持作用，将阻止改变，这就是引力质量。引力质量和惯性质量，都是空间体系保持自身空间属性的能力。

惯性质量和引力质量是不同的。引力质量与惯性质量的不同点在于：

引力质量对外表现是因为相对空间视角的变化，在基本力的作用下导致能量的变化，其对外表现不需要相对空间的转换，引力质量不随速度变化。

惯性质量对外表现是因为相对空间转换的过程中出现的能量变化，其对外表现必须通过相对空间的转换，惯性质量跟随速度变化。

反引力空间体系与万有引力空间体系相比较，其相对空间作用是相反的。

也就是说，在相对空间的改变中，需要考虑粒子双方的相对空间作用方向。随着相对空间作用方向的不同，在相对空间变化的过程中，能量差的增加或减少，都可以使动能增加，也可以使动能减少。

光子（或电磁波）不拥有自己的相对空间，所以不存在相对空间的转换，也就不会呈现相对空间转换过程中的惯性质量（静止质量）。光子在宇宙空间中传播，它属于整个宇宙空间，由于基本作用力遵循视角原理，在宇宙空间中的传播过程中，光子呈现引力质量，并且呈现出引力质量的部分性质。

Chapter 3: The Principle of Gravity and the Quantum Gravity Equation

It is known that Mr. Einstein, in his general theory of relativity, used the gravitational field equations to describe how matter in spacetime affects and bends the geometric space of spacetime around it through its mass, and that the curved spacetime affects the motion of matter, i.e., the spacetime tells the object how to move, and the object tells the spacetime how to bend. General relativity explains many phenomena that Newton's theory of gravity cannot explain. However, according to the important oversight I have discovered in human measurements of the speed of light (described in the first chapter of this paper), that oversight has been enough to shake the theoretical foundations of relativity.

In quantum mechanics, the hypothesis of gravitons has been proposed, but unfortunately no evidence for their existence has been found until now.

Except for the above two most representative theories, people have different opinions about the formation principle of gravity, but none of them can come close to the truth.

I did not refer to anyone's writings when thinking about the principle of gravity. Intuition told me that all the laws of physics must have an underlying logic and must be compatible with each other. So, I started with motion, relative space, and slowly drew my way to the principle of gravity. The principle is simple and straightforward, and ultimately

capable of being extended, with no problems in doing so.

1. The principle of universal gravitation

A and B are two relatively stationary particles. In A and B, the electromagnetic waves within them propagate at the speed of light in their own spatial system, and the two particles do not have any interaction when only A exists in space, or when only B exists in space (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1: When observing relative space independently

When observing two particles A and B in space at the same time, the two particles appear in each other's view angle changes. As in Figure 3.2, A and B are separated by a distance of R . When observing B from the viewpoint of A, B is in a cone with A as its vertex; the larger the distance from B, the smaller the angle of the cone of view, and the smaller the distance, the larger the angle of the cone of view. There are countless points on the surface of the sphere with A as the center and R as the radius, which are equivalent to point B. A and B exist in different relative spaces. The ultimate basic principle of gravity can be found by combining the relative spaces based on the cone of view.

Figure 3.2: Perspective cone between relative spaces

Take B at any position on the sphere and observe it together with A as in Fig. 3.3:

Figure 3.3: Perspective cone between relative spaces

Inside two particles, A and B, their electromagnetic waves travel at the speed of light in their respective space systems. When one of the particles is observed alone, its electromagnetic wave has no effect on the other spatial system.

When the two particles are observed simultaneously: the electromagnetic wave of B propagates in the relative space of B at the same time as it propagates in the cone of view of A; the electromagnetic wave of A propagates in the relative space of A at the same time as it propagates in the cone of view of B.

The following two effects can be deduced from Figure

3.3:

I, the relative space of A with all the electromagnetic waves it contains forms a perspective on the relative space beyond A. The total amount of electromagnetic waves of A acts on the perspective cone to form the density and structure of the Viewing Angle.

When the total amount of electromagnetic waves of A increases or decreases, it causes the density of the Viewing Angle to increase or decrease.

II, the electromagnetic wave inside B in the process of propagation, relative to the relative space of A (Viewing Angle of A) appears to change the density of the relative space:

In the direction toward A, the density of the electromagnetic waves of B relative to the relative space of A increases with time;

In the direction away from A, the density of the electromagnetic wave of B relative to the relative space of A decreases with time.

Electromagnetic waves of B relative to the relative space of A produce an overall difference in the tendency to A -- the electromagnetic waves of B passing through the relative space belonging to A, sparse away from A, dense near A. In the relative space of A (Viewing Angle of A), the electromagnetic waves of B have an overall tendency to A.

Combining I and II shows that the overall energy trend

toward A appears in the electromagnetic waves of B under the effect of the density and structure of A's perspective, and this trend creates an energy differential toward A. It is this that leads to gravity.

When the perspectives of A and B are swapped the result is unchanged.

Perspectives can be superimposed, and both A and B can be all the atoms of an object, or an ocean, or a planet, or a galaxy.

--This is the "Principle of Gravity" obtained under the new idea.

2. Quantum gravity equation

According to the "Principle of Gravity", the quantum gravity equation can be derived and the correctness of the principle can be further proved.

In this derivation process, energy is used to explain the relevant equations.

Figure 3.4: particle A's "relative space" and "relative space contains the energy" on the particle B formed by the perspective of

Figure 3.4: Density of relative spatial interactions

the role of the particle B formed in the particle B to R as the radius of the sphere.

Enlarging Figure 3.4 locally, we get Figure 3.5, in which the distance between particle A and particle B is R, the mass of particle A is M, the energy is E, the mass of particle B is m, the energy is e, the circumference is π , the distance between particle A and particle B is R, the mass of particle A is M, the energy is E, the mass of particle B is m, the energy is e, the circumference is π .

Figure 3.5: Density of relative spatial interactions

All the energy of A acts, with respect to B, on a sphere with A as the center and R as the radius, then the relative spatial action density (energy density) at particle A with respect to particle B is $\frac{E}{4\pi R^2}$.

According to the Principle of Gravity, there is an energy difference in the space of action of particle B with respect to A. The energy propagating in all directions in particle B can be simplified (as in Fig. 3.6) by considering only the part of the energy ab^+ , directed towards A that produces gravitational force, its quantity is $(1/2)^3$.

As shown in Figure 3.6, in the $ab \leftarrow$ energy $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3$. Part of the energy outside the θ angle is required to cancel out the

Figure 3.6: Energy difference under relative space action

energy moving away from A in the $ab \rightarrow$ direction and is not accounted for in equation. The amount of energy within the θ angle, which is $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta$, produces a tendency toward A.

The energy trend produced is the part of the energy $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta$, which in the process of propagation in the direction of A, there is an increase in energy density due to compression in the cone of view of A, the "amount of increase in energy density" forms the energy difference Δe . When calculating Δe , according to the Uncertainty Principle, it is not possible to calculate the change in volume of the cone of view with respect to A in the geometrical space of the particle B. It is necessary to consider all the energy propagating in B as propagating in the relative space of A. Then, relative to the space of particle A, the electromagnetic wave in particle B propagates in all directions, forming a sphere of electromagnetic waves with the center of mass of particle B as the sphere. Corresponding to the area $\frac{1}{4\pi R^2}$ of the relative spatial action of particle A with respect to particle B, the

volume of the cone of view of particle B with respect to A changes by $\frac{1}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$. Then, the energy difference $\Delta e = \frac{e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$ that appears in the space of action of particle B relative to A.

The relative spatial action density (energy density) of A multiplied by the energy change of B is the "energy that causes B to be attracted to A".

The following equations are formed when combined:

$$\frac{F}{g} c^2 = \frac{E}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 e \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$$

Get the **quantum gravity equation**:

$$F = \frac{M c^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 m c^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$$

Simplified equation:

$$F = \frac{M m}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin \theta}{128\pi^2 c}$$

where c is the speed of light and g is the acceleration of gravity on the ground. Where $\frac{3g \sin \theta}{128\pi^2 c}$ is the mathematical expression for the "universal gravitational constant", if the particle A is regarded as the earth, its physical meaning is: the gravitational coefficient between the unit space energy density of the earth relative to the ground object and the unit energy of the ground object.

In the equation $F = \frac{M c^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 m c^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$, the relative spatial action of particle A with respect to particle B at particle

B, $\frac{1}{4\pi R^2}$, and the change in the volume of particle B with respect to A's cone of perspectives, $\frac{1}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3}$, are at the center of the principle of gravity described in this paper.

In the equation, the energy of the particle is calculated using Einstein's mass-energy equation $E = mc^2$, the circumference π is calculated at 3.141592654, the speed of light c is 299,792,458 m/s, and the acceleration of gravity g is considered a constant, and is calculated at 9.807. The value of the θ -angle is shown in Fig. 3.6, and when the value of the θ -angle is taken to be 60° or less, this portion of the energy forms gravitational force.

将数据代入公式得 $\frac{3g \sin 60}{128\pi^2 c}$,

Substituting the data into the formula $\frac{3g \sin 60}{128\pi^2 c}$, the value of the "universal gravitational constant" is 6.72736×10^{-11} , which is less than 0.795% different from the original value of 6.67387×10^{-11} . The reason: the equation $F = \frac{Mm}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin 60}{128\pi^2 c}$ is quantum gravity, which is slightly larger than the gravitational force of the object measured on the ground.

The first reason is that in the equation, $e \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 \cdot \sin 60$ approximates the energy ab^+ , which can be calculated in a more precise way in the future;

The second reason is that in the actual measurements on the ground, the density variations of the Earth's rotation, the Earth's radius and the layers of the Earth's structure are not negligible, resulting in slightly smaller measured values than

the quantum gravity values, and the θ -angle should be taken to be slightly less than 60° . It can also be understood that the ground measurement is the gravitational force of the particles relative to the "collection of particles of the Earth", due to the uneven density of the Earth, the closer the density of the Earth's center the greater, then the value of the θ angle should also be slightly less than 60° .

According to the calculation, when the value of θ angle is about 59.22° , the gravitational equation $F = \frac{Mm}{R^2} \cdot \frac{3g \sin 59.22}{128\pi^2 c}$ is formed, and the result of the calculation is completely in line with the results measured on the ground.

2.3 Universality of the quantum gravity equation

The quantum gravity equation has maximum universality and can be applied to various reference systems. In the quantum gravity equation:

$$F = \frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 mc^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$$

The physical meaning of $\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3$ is that the electromagnetic wave sphere with particle B's center of mass as the sphere's center is at the speed of light in any direction, and the gravitational force generated has nothing to do with particle B's state of motion, no matter in what way particle B is moving, and no matter how high the speed of particle B's motion is, if the "relative spatial action" of particle A already exists in the relative space of B, the objective basis of the quantum gravity equation will not be changed. In the

formation process of gravity, all the energy does not need to be converted between the relative spaces, following the principle of invariance of the speed of light, the "mass-energy increment" caused by the relative motion of particles has nothing to do with the formation of gravity.

In addition, the reason g is considered a constant in the text is that during the development of physics, a series of ground-based regulations for mass, energy, force, length, speed, acceleration, etc. have been made, and g is an intrinsic constant that has been formed between these physical metrics.

2.4 Gravitational equations for massive stars

The above quantum gravity equations, when applied to massive stars, need to consider the ratio of the blue-shift and red-shift of the electromagnetic waves due to the gravitational pull of the massive star. In Fig. 3.5, if a is a massive star, the gravitational force of a will cause the energy of b to appear gravitationally blue shifted and gravitationally redshifted, and the same electromagnetic wave will have more energy in the blue shifted direction than in the redshifted direction, so that the relative spatial action of the massive star on the object is greater, then the relative spatial action density of a at the point of b is $\frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{f_b}{f_r}$, where f_b is the electromagnetic wave blueshift frequency, and f_r is the redshift frequency. The gravitational equations for massive stars are obtained: $F =$

$$\frac{Mc^2}{4\pi R^2} \cdot \frac{f_b}{f_r} \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^3 mc^2 \cdot \sin \theta}{\frac{4}{3}\pi c^3} \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}$$

Chapter 4: Ways to Overcome Gravity, Universal Repulsion, and Anti-Gravity Models

Guided by the principle of gravity, and based on the concepts of relative space, relative spatial action, relative spatial transformation, energy difference and energy trend, and continuing to derive thinking, you can deduce a way to overcome the force of gravity.

1. Analysis of the principle of overcoming gravity by the rotation of artificial Earth satellites around the Earth

Among all the methods of overcoming the force of gravity, the rotation of artificial Earth satellites around the Earth is one of the earliest methods discovered by mankind and is also well known.

We generally overcome the force of gravity by circular or elliptical motion, and we say that circular or elliptical motion creates centrifugal force, which has been defined as the force of inertia. When thinking deeply about gravity and antigravity, we can find that people's definitions do not go deep enough to understand the deeper principles of matter, and defining centrifugal force as an inertial force is still an image-only theory.

As in Figure 4.1, suppose A is the Earth and B is an artificial satellite. If B and A are at rest relative to each other, B will be attracted by the gravitational force between A and B

under the action of the cone of view of A. Eventually, B will fall on Earth A.

Now we accelerate B to the first cosmic velocity in the tangential direction of Earth A.

At this point we say that B generates a centrifugal force, the inertial force, relative to A. Under the action of this force B will move in a circular motion around Earth A.

So, what is the principle of centrifugal force? --The principle can be analyzed in terms of relative spatial transformations.

Before describing the principle of centrifugal force, it is important to understand that there is a key difference between centrifugal force and gravity:

Gravity: caused by the perspective between the two space systems, the relative spatial action has nothing to do with the state of motion of the two space systems, so no matter what way A and B move, and no matter how high or low the relative speed of motion, gravity always exists.

Centrifugal force: belongs to the process of motion generated by the role of force, the role follows the characteristics of the movement, there is no difference between A and B until there is a relative spatial transformation. When considering the relative spatial transition, B relative to

Figure 4.1: Centrifugal force principle for artificial satellites

A appears in the direction of motion of the energy difference.

As in Fig. 4.2.1, we simplify the electromagnetic waves inside B and keep only the electromagnetic waves propagating in the direction of motion and in the opposite direction of motion. According to the description of the principle of motion of the gravitational principle, to scrutinize the force generated when B moves with respect to A, it is necessary to find the energy difference of B with respect to A (energy trend).

Figure 4.1: Centrifugal force principle for artificial satellites

As in Figure 4.2.2, after the completion of the relative spatial conversion:

Electromagnetic wave W_1 is converted to W_1' , the wavelength becomes smaller, the frequency becomes larger, and the energy becomes larger;

Electromagnetic wave W_2 is converted to W_2' , the wavelength becomes longer, the frequency becomes smaller, and the energy becomes smaller.

Thus, B has an overall energy difference in the direction

of motion, and this energy difference forms the centrifugal force.

The above is the fundamental principle of centrifugal force.

In circular motion, the energy difference formed by the motion of B is away from A at any time, and its effect is equal in size and opposite in direction to the energy difference (energy trend) caused by gravity.

2. The second special case of planar particles

Particle A is an ordinary particle and particle B is a planar shaped particle with the plane of particle B perpendicular to the line joining AB as in Fig. 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Second special case of planar particles

In particle B, all the electromagnetic waves contained in particle B are rotating and propagating at the circular edge of B. The propagation direction of electromagnetic waves follows the waveform oscillation, presenting clockwise propagation at one moment (as in Fig. 4.3.1) and

counterclockwise propagation at the next moment (as in Fig. 4.3.2). At this point we analyze the energy difference (energy trend) of particle B relative to particle A by relative spatial transformation.

As shown in Figure 4.3.3, after the completion of the relative spatial transformation, the propagation direction of all electromagnetic waves is perpendicular to the tangent line of B, and perpendicular to the "tangent point of B and the line connecting A". Currently, all the energy of the particle B shows a tendency to move away from the energy of A, and the particle B shows a complete repulsive effect relative to the particle A.

Examining Fig. 4.3.1 and Fig. 4.3.2, when the electromagnetic wave of particle B is not converted into relative space, all the electromagnetic waves are also perpendicular to the "line connecting the tangent point of B and A", and the particle B and the particle A are also repulsive. The principle of this situation is the same as that of the "universal gravitation between two ordinary particles", which I name the universal repulsion. The universal repulsion is of the same nature as the universal gravitation, but in the opposite direction, and is a long-range force.

Particle B is the particle model of neutrino.

On this basis, six basic forces can be classified.

Universal repulsion can be classified as the fifth fundamental force based on the fourth fundamental force. In addition, the chemical bonding force formed by electrons outside the nucleus and, in molecules, by two or more

electrons, can be classified as the sixth fundamental force.

A particle such as particle B, while moving in the vertical line of its plane without being affected by inertia, can exceed the speed of light due to the repulsive force between it and a star, provided that the spatial action of the star already exists in the space through which the particle passes. On the other hand, the existence of repulsive action between such a particle and other particles, and the greater the repulsive force the closer the particle is, makes it difficult for it to collide with other particles even if it is moving at a very high speed, and it can even pass through dense solids with ease. This is the perfect explanation for the FTL neutrino phenomenon, i.e., it explains the principle of neutrino action and the FTL phenomenon.

Back in 2011, I had closely followed the discovery of FTL neutrinos at the European Center for Nuclear Research (CERN), and unfortunately the publicly available information showed that the tests were a failure. But my theory supports them.

One can mimic this particle model to overcome gravity.

3. Several types of anti-gravity devices

The first type:

As in Fig. 4.4, a superconducting coil is wound around a horizontal circular plane that can be rotated around a vertical axis and held in place. By introducing a certain amount of electrical energy, a lifting force opposite to the direction of gravity is generated. Alternatively, a laser can be fed into a

fiber optic coil fixed in a circular shape.

Figure 4.4: Winding a superconducting coil on a flat surface

The amount of lift is proportional to the energy input and inversely proportional to the square of the distance from the center of mass of the star.

The key to all the ways we are going to overcome gravity is to be able to create an overall energy difference along the spherical tangent of the star's space of action, creating a tendency to move away.

It is foreseeable that when the energy input is large enough, a force greater than the force of gravity can be generated to accelerate the device away from Earth, making space travel over large distances a simple matter. Legendary flying saucers, must have gotten their force to overcome gravity in this way.

The second type:

A disc with a large diameter placed in a horizontal plane, with a large mass at the edge of the disc and a smaller mass at the center, when the whole disc is spinning at a super-high speed, and the linear velocity at the edge of the disc exceeds the first cosmic velocity, the disc will acquire an

antigravitational force as the rotational speed is increased.

The third type

Make a lighter mass and larger energy circular high-energy particle accelerator, in the accelerator through the magnetic field to control many high-energy particles running in the circular orbit, when the total kinetic energy of all the high-energy particles to meet the requirements of antigravity, the same can be obtained antigravity.

The fourth type

The "second special case of plane-shaped particles" is imitated in an annular or spherical container. It is necessary to make all the electromagnetic waves or photons in the plane or container show circular oscillation by controlling the propagation path of electromagnetic waves on the plane perpendicular to the line connecting the gravitational center of gravity as shown in Fig. 4.4. When human science and technology develops to a higher level, the fourth way directly imitates the "second special case of plane-shaped particles", and satisfies the conditions for the formation of the fifth basic force, it will become the best way to overcome the force of gravity.

The common denominator of all anti-gravity devices is the formation of a rotating energy difference in the ring around the perpendicular to the line of gravity.

In the future, mankind can take many ways to overcome the effects of gravity and become an interstellar civilization under the guidance of the Creator.

Chapter 5: A Few Thought Experiments and Reflections on Gravity and Antigravity

In the previous two chapters, we learned about the principles of gravity and anti-gravity. If we look at them from God's perspective, we can get several special forms of gravity and anti-gravity, as well as the special form of the connection between the relative space of the particles and the space of the universe. It is these special forms that make our universe has the supreme selflessness and virtue, with infinite future and infinite possibilities, the universe will not become a "collapse-explosion" cycle or a super black hole, and there is no end of the Thermal Silence or death.

These special forms are briefly described below:

1. Gravity is not always mutual

To explain this knowledge, which is far beyond common sense, let's have a super thought experiment. Of course, the following thought experiment is something one would not dare to think about, much less write about in any paper. But to explain that gravity is not always a mutual force, this experiment must be expounded.

Let us suppose that God, who is supremely good and omnipotent, wanted one day to enjoy the beauty of the earth and snapped his fingers, pause the entire solar system. temporarily canceling all mutual forces between the planets

and all the light that had been emitted. All the planets could not see the other planets, and all could not see anyone else.

..... He took away the earth for a while - to show the beauty of the earth in heaven.

Then God made the effects of the ringing finger disappear. The sun reemitted its light, and the light began to spread. A little time passed and the sunlight reached the original location of the earth, and the sun froze, where did the earth go? Since the Earth was not found, the Sun could not feel the Earth's gravity.

Of course, the sun needed to be busy with a lot of things, and it was too late to think about where the Earth had gone, and the light continued to propagate.

After a few seconds, God put the earth back in its place.

After putting it back in place rang his fingers! The second ringing of the fingers only pauses and does not cancel everything.

At this point, it is certainly possible to imagine what gravity looks like at this moment.

At this moment: the sun's rays are already shining at the location of the Earth, and the Sun's outward action relative to space is already present at this location of the Earth.

The Earth is immediately affected by the gravitational force of the Sun.

However, the matter of the Earth being put back into its original position is not yet seen or known by the Sun, because the Earth's space of action has not yet passed over to the Sun's side, and the Sun is not affected by the Earth's universal

gravitational force!

At this point, we discover something that can't happen in regular physics: the forces of gravity are not always mutual.

Then the effects of the second ringing finger disappeared and all continued.

Eight minutes later, the Sun saw the light reflected from the Earth, and the spatial effects of the Earth propagated to the Sun's position.

The Sun feels the Earth's gravity again. Then everything in the solar system returned to normal.

This thought experiment showed one thing: gravity is not always mutual, and completely broke through the "relativity of forces". This is the problem with mechanics, where people always assume that forces are transmitted by matter or particles - this is not the case, and we are all too lost in the delusion to see the truth. If you go deeper and add an additional problem, it is that all mechanics needs to consider the speed of light, and needs to consider God's perspective.

Gravity does not travel over distance in real time, gravity at large scales is not always mutual, this feature keeps the universe stable.

Electromagnetic waves in particles and the relative space of particles have a "relative spatial effect" on external space. This relative action cannot exceed the speed of light. When a particle is created, its effect on space travels at the speed of light, and when that effect travels to other particles, the other particles begin to be gravitated by that particle. If the "spatial action" of the other particles already existed before the

particle was created, at the location where the particle was created, the particle is immediately subject to the gravitational pull of the other particles from the moment of its creation. The other particles will not be gravitated by the other particles until the spatial action of the particle has propagated to the position of the other particles. Gravity is not always mutual, depending on the existence and propagation of the "spatial action".

2. Antigravity is not always mutual.

The latter thought experiment is even simpler, but the reasoning will be even deeper: at some point, an antigravity device (hereinafter referred to as a "flying saucer") suddenly operates for half a second at an altitude of 300,000 kilometers above the Earth, and then shuts down.

During the half-second of the flying saucers "run", the flying saucer was subjected to the Earth's antigravity.

The Earth began to be subjected to the antigravitational force of the flying saucer about half a second after the saucer shut down, and it "lasted for half-a-second". During the "two half-a-seconds" period, the force on both was unidirectional.

In the half-a-second after the saucer shut down, before the Earth received the saucer's counter-gravity, there was no counter-gravity between the two.

Of course, one can explain all this in terms of "spacetime", and it's self-consistent in your pathetic theories. However, in the future, when people use quantum

entanglement to fully realize the "real-time" and "super-distance" transmission of information, and when they use flying saucers to realize super-light travel, do they also have to adhere to the fallacy of space-time? The so-called "space-time" has been hindering the development of science for nearly a hundred years, and even if human life span is measured in 200 years, the radius of the light sphere we live in is only a pitiful 200 light years. Don't people want to break through this pathetic cognitive barrier?

Of course, if you insist on the idea of space-time, then I'll give you another test to see how you can explain it all in terms of space-time.

3. Forces are not always reciprocal in large-scale space

Suppose there is a giant Earth-scale flying saucer traveling at hypervelocity at 1 light-year from the Earth. At this location, the relative spatial action of the Sun and the Earth already exists in the flight path of the saucer (this relative spatial action was emitted by the Sun and the Earth one year ago). At some point, the saucer utilized the counter gravity generated by the relative spatial interaction of the Sun and the Earth to reduce its flight speed, and after about 10 minutes, the saucer achieved its goal of slowing down and temporarily shut down and ceased the action of the counter gravity. Since the saucer was a giant saucer on the scale of the Earth, the counter-gravitational force generated by it was so

great that if the Earth had been subjected to that force a year later, it would have been very noticeable, could even have catastrophic consequences.

After six months, the saucer Sweep by 100 million kilometers from the Earth and flew off into the distance.

Another six months later, the relative spatial action of the saucer, which can generate an antigravitational force, passed through the sun and the Earth "where they were two years ago". At this moment, neither the Earth nor the Sun was subjected to the ten-minute-long antigravity force emitted by the saucer a year earlier. Possible catastrophe didn't happen.

Corollary: forces do not always act on each other.

4. The effect of antigravity on close objects

Since antigravity, like gravity, exhibits an inverse square relationship with distance. Humans can cleverly design the flying saucer, so that the antigravity force can push the flying saucer to overcome the gravitational force to do ultra-high acceleration movement at the same time, push the flying saucer "living beings and every particle of the object" to move with the same acceleration, to achieve super-light speed with ultra-high acceleration to realize the real freedom of interstellar journey.

When the anti-gravity force is strong enough, it will form a strong enough repulsive force on objects in proximity that any approaching matter will be dramatically slowed down (by

applying a large reverse acceleration to the object), forming an "energy shield" centered on the saucer, as fantasized in the special effects of the movies. Under the action of the anti-gravity force in a specific direction, it can slow down the speed of the object that crashes into the saucer at high speed to zero, and then realize the rebound.

At the same time, the material molecules around the antigravity device will also be subjected to repulsive force, so that the antigravity device isolates the air molecules and water molecules, supersonic movement in the air will not appear sonic boom, and movement in the ocean by the water resistance will also be very small. If the repulsive force generated by the anti-gravity device is strong enough to isolate all particles moving at high speeds, it would be able to enter the inner magma of the Earth, and even enter the interior of a star.

5. Limitations of the law of conservation of energy

The energy of a flying saucer increases to such an extent that a repulsive force greater than the force of gravity will be generated at any location in space, after which the saucer will accelerate away from the Earth. Predictably, to overcome gravity, the energy input to the coil must exceed the kinetic energy possessed to overcome the first cosmic velocity. When the flying saucer leaves the gravitational range of the Earth, the same methods described above can be used to overcome the gravitational pull of even more powerful planets, or even

galaxies, on the way to true interstellar freedom. As long as the energy of the flying saucer is high enough to keep accelerating at a high rate of speed to move away from the Earth, and to keep accelerating at a high rate of speed to decelerate when it reaches its destination, it can take only a few minutes to get from the Earth to the Moon, and a few hours, or less, to get to Mars.

The principle of antigravity generated by flying saucers is completely different from the physics and mechanics that people have summarized before. It even violates two of the most important laws of previous physics:

One is that it doesn't need to throw matter to realize the reaction force, which would violate the law of conservation of momentum if not explained by this theory I've provided;

The second is that the velocity away will increase with time as the effects of the force of gravity are overcome, at which point the increase in velocity does not require the expenditure of more energy. This kind of motion will fundamentally impact the traditional kinetic and potential energy theory system, and produce irreconcilable contradictions with the most important law in traditional physics, the law of conservation of energy.

The reason for this contradiction is, firstly, that the concept of "relative spatial action" has not been introduced into the law of conservation of energy. Secondly, if we continue to explore the law of conservation of energy, we will find that it is not that energy is not conserved, but that the law of conservation of energy has certain limitations - it does not

define and explain kinetic energy and potential energy in a deeper sense. And to explain kinetic and potential energy requires a deeper understanding of electromagnetic waves and their relative space.

6. Redefining potential energy

Potential energy is different in nature from kinetic energy, and distinguishing between them requires a more in-depth exploration of the effects of gravity on spatial systems.

As in Figure 5.1, suppose A is the Earth and B is a particle. When B is higher from the ground, B produces a smaller energy difference (energy trend) in the cone of view of A. When B is lower from the ground, B produces a larger energy difference (energy trend) in the cone of view of A. There is a difference in the energy difference (energy trend) between B at two different distances, and that difference is the change in potential energy.

The change in the potential energy of a particle is caused by the degree of difference in the imbalance of the

electromagnetic waves in the particle relative to another spatial system at different spatial distances. Relative to the Earth's space of action, the lower you are from the ground, the greater this relative imbalance and the smaller the potential energy; at higher locations the relative imbalance is smaller and the potential energy is greater. This is a discussion of potential energy in terms of its nature, which does not contradict the quantitative description of potential energy.

At a certain height, this relative space imbalance is at a certain level, and if the height is changed, it must cause a change in the degree of imbalance. Due to the relative space of the particles and their electromagnetic waves composed of the space system of space properties of the maintenance of the role, will prevent the change, which is the gravitational mass. Gravitational mass and inertial mass, are the ability of the space system to maintain its own spatial properties.

Inertial mass and gravitational mass are different. The difference between gravitational mass and inertial mass is this:

Gravitational mass outwardly manifests itself because of the change in relative spatial perspective, which leads to a change in energy under the action of the fundamental force, and its outward manifestation does not require a relative spatial transformation, gravitational mass does not vary with velocity;

Inertial mass is manifested externally because of the energy change that occurs in the process of relative space conversion, and its external manifestation must be transformed through relative space, inertial mass follows

velocity.

Antigravitational space system compared with the universal gravitational space system, its relative space role is opposite.

In the change of relative space, it is necessary to consider the direction of relative spatial action of both sides of the particle. With the different direction of relative spatial action, the increase or decrease of the energy difference in the process of relative spatial change can make the kinetic energy increase or decrease.

Photons (or electromagnetic waves) do not possess their own relative space, so there is no relative space conversion, and they do not present inertial mass (rest mass) in the process of relative space conversion. Photons propagate in cosmic space, which belongs to the entire cosmic space, and because the fundamental forces follow the Viewing Angle Principle (the following chapter for details), photons present gravitational mass and exhibit some of the properties of gravitational mass during propagation in cosmic space.